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A review of inflatable solar dryers for drying fruits, vegetables, and grain

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Abstract

This paper presents the features, advantages, and applications of inflatable solar dryers in drying food products, such as fruits, vegetables, and grain. The inflatable solar dryer is a further development of the Hohenheim-type solar tunnel dryer. Due to its low maintenance, environment-friendly, hassle-free, and portable characteristics, the inflatable solar dryer is a favourable alternative for sun drying in rural areas and could be used to obtain high-quality dried food products. The paper may help farmers and researchers for the improvement of this type of dryer.

Keywords: inflatable solar dryer; fruits; vegetables; grain.

Introduction

Drying is an energy-intensive process and solar drying is therefore a preferred method in developing countries with limited resources. Recent studies have focused on the development of solar dryers. In this case, the inflatable solar dryer (ISD) or solar bubble dryer (SBD) is a further development of the Hohenheim-type solar tunnel dryer and is composed of a transparent, ultraviolet (UV)-resistant plastic [e.g., polythene (PE)] top cover and a black reinforced plastic [e.g., polyvinyl chloride (PVC)] drying floor connected by a heavy-duty zipper (see Figure 1). The ISD is inflated using a fan, and therefore it does not need any solid structure as the fan inflates the dryer forming a tunnel; thus, it is collapsible and can easily be transported. Through the transparent top cover, solar radiation enters the drying tunnel and heats the food products being dried. Moisture is then evaporated and pushed out by the fan from the tunnel. The

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fan provides ventilation for an even distribution of heat and airflow for moisture removal. The fan is driven by a photovoltaic system for off-grid operation [1, 2].

Figure 1. A schematic diagram of an ISD [2].

Features and advantages of Inflatible solar dryers

The ISD is a low-cost drying technology that aims to provide a simple and flexible alternative to sun drying. The main purpose of the ISD is to protect food products from rain, transform solar energy into heat, and lead the drying air over the food products. The ISD uses locally available materials, thus making it economical to build. To ensure that the food products dry evenly, a simple roller with ropes attached to both of its ends is periodically dragged underneath to mix the food products without the need to open the tunnel [3]. Lastly, this dryer has been used to dry a plurality of food products, such as grain, beans, fruits, and vegetables.

Grain

Salvatierra-Rojas *et al.* [3] developed an ISD for drying rice in the Philippines during both rainy and dry seasons. Sun drying and shade drying were performed in parallel for comparison and rice was evaluated for moisture content and quality in terms of milling recovery and head rice yield. Moisture content was reduced from 23% to 14% (wet basis) within 26-52 hours of continuous operation during the rainy season and 16% to 14% within 4-26 hours of drying during the dry season. In both seasons, the final moisture content of 12% was reached after prolonged drying periods. Quality was not affected concerning drying treatment. However, condensation was encountered on the floor of the ISD in some batches during the rainy season experiments.

In Ethiopia, Asemu *et al.* [4] designed an ISD to study the drying behaviour of freshly harvested corn grain. The performance of the ISD was tested at sample loads of 10.87 kg/m² (thin layer), 16.3 kg/m² (medium layer), and 21.74 kg/m² (thick layer)

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under two mixing conditions, 2- and 3-hour intervals. BH-540 and BH-660 corn cultivars at 22-29% (wet basis) moisture content were used. The required drying time was highly dependent on the sample load. About 24 hours were required to dry the grain to 13% (wet basis) moisture in the thin-layer compared to 39 hours in the thick-layer. More frequent mixing of corn (2-hour intervals) shortened the drying time by 5-17%.

Figure 2. External (left) and internal (right) views of an ISD [3].

Beans

In the Philippines, Oria and Palconit [5] studied the drying of coffee beans in an ISD, which incorporates steel cans as solar air heaters (SAHs). The steel cans boost the temperature of entering air into the chamber and gradually provide heated air temperature to the bottom parts of the food products (e.g., coffee beans, corn grain).

Figure 3. Design of an ISD with integrated SAHs [5].

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The results reveal that 3 batches of 16.3 kg coffee beans may be dried to an ideal moisture content of 12% (wet basis) on the third day or an exact period of 27 hours of drying. However, drying the same amount of coffee beans in the open sun takes 5 days or 47 hours [5].

Tenorio-Herrera and Urbina-Cornavaca [6] investigated the drying of freshly fermented cocoa beans in Nicaragua. The moisture content of 84.6 kg cocoa beans was reduced from 50% down to 7.4% (wet basis) within 5 days, which corresponds to 25.5 accumulated hours of solar radiation. The temperature of cocoa beans was always below the maximum allowable limit (i.e., 65 °C). Shock *et al.* [7] reported the drying of kidney beans (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) in Uganda. The results show that the drying temperature was approximately 10 °C higher in the ISD compared to the open sun drying. The drying strategy during the night had no considerable effect on the product quality.

Fruits

van-Hung *et al.* [8] studied the drying of oyster mushrooms (*Pleurotus ostreatus*). The ISD includes a perforated elevated floor on which the mushrooms are placed. The perforated floor consists of a net and supporting frame made of inflated plastic beams to be deflated together with the ISD when they are not in use. This modification enables the drying air to move both on the top and underneath the mushrooms increasing drying efficiency and preventing the mushrooms from sticking on the bottom, thus avoiding rewetting the mushrooms (see Figure 4). This converted the drying process from overflow drying to a hybrid of overflow drying combined with flow-through drying. The moisture content of oyster mushrooms was reduced from 90% down to 40-60% within 2-4 hours, thus corresponding to the drying rate at this stage of 10-20% h⁻¹. At the next stage, it took about 4-6 hours corresponding to a drying rate of 2-10% h⁻¹ to reach the required product moisture content of 8-10%.

Figure 4. A schematic diagram of an ISD with a perforated floor [8].

Zewdu [9] used a modified ISD that includes a chamber frame (i.e., a rectangular hollow steel) and a perforated floor for drying of red pepper (*Capsicum* L.) in Ethiopia. The results showed that the moisture content was reduced from 71 to

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13% (wet basis) in 20 hours of operation. This was achieved within 5 days of experiments for 4 hours per day at a drying rate of 0.1 kg/h. The total drying time was 20 hours that saves 20% of the drying time when compared with open sun drying.

In general, the ISD with an added perforated elevated floor ensured the quality without any requirement of mixing or turning the food products during drying.

Watson *et al.* [10] investigated the drying of red chili (*Capsicum L.*) using small- and large-scale ISD in California and India. The average total time to dry red chili from 70-80% to 10-12% (wet basis) in 4 small-scale trials and 1 large-scale trial was reduced by more than 50% compared to open sun drying. The maximum temperatures recorded in the small-scale and large-scale trials were 79 and 69 °C, respectively.

Vegetables

Romuli *et al.* [11] reported the drying of Amaranth (*Amaranthus L.*) leaves using an ISD. To handle the drying of lightweight materials, a modification was made to the ISD by adding an air deflector and trays inside the ISD. The air deflector prevents blowing away the vegetable leaves from the trays. The air deflector was in the preheating area. To place the vegetable leaves, 21 trays covered with 4x4 mm wire mesh, each with 1065x860 mm surface area were lined up inside the ISD. The temperature inside the ISD could reach up to 69.4 °C during the day and 13.4 °C during the night (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. Placement of trays on wooden frames inside the ISD [11].

Conclusions

An inflatable solar dryer (ISD) or solar bubble dryer (SBD) has the potential to be adopted by small farmers in developing countries, especially in rural areas, to improve the quality of dried food products. The ISD is portable and completely independent of fuel or the power grid, and is, therefore, very cheap to operate. Furthermore, the ISD improves qualitatively and quantitatively the traditional sun-drying process.

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